

ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF NEW EARLY-MATURING, HIGH-YIELDING MAIZE VARIETIES AND THEIR PRIMARY SEED PRODUCTION

Kh.K. Nazarov¹, T.Kh. Farmanov², K.K. Azizov³

Tashkent State Agrarian University, Associate Professor of the Department of Genetics,
Breeding and Seed Production of Agricultural Crops, Doctor of Agricultural Sciences (DSc)¹

Tashkent State University of Economics, Professor, Doctor of Economics²

Research Institute of Cereals and Leguminous Crops, Deputy Director for Research and
Innovation, Doctor of Agricultural Sciences (DSc), Senior Researcher³

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20812058>

Abstract. *This article examines scientific research on maize cultivation for grain and green fodder production, the research developments of scientists, and the newly developed early-maturing and high-yielding maize variety “Kelajak 100”, which is intended for grain and green fodder production. A comparative analysis was conducted between the new variety and the widely cultivated standard variety “Uzbekistan 601 ECB”. The study analyzes varietal differences, yield levels, production costs, total income, net profit, and overall economic efficiency. On the basis of the obtained results, the economic effectiveness of the new “Kelajak 100” variety is scientifically substantiated.*

Keywords: *maize grain, seed production, yield, output, green fodder, production costs, income, profit, profitability level, value, promising variety, hybrid variety.*

1. Introduction

Maize is one of the most widely cultivated cereal crops in the world and is grown for fodder, food, and industrial purposes. Its grain contains 65-70% carbohydrates, 9-12% protein, 4-8% oil, mineral salts, and vitamins. In terms of cultivated area and yield, the United States ranks first, China second, and Brazil third.

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) remains a major food source in many regions of the world. According to United Nations data cited in the source text, global grain production is approximately 2.45 billion tonnes, of which around 2.194 billion tonnes are accounted for by cereal crops, including maize.

Globally, 116 million tonnes of maize are used as food. In addition, maize is an important source of starch for the pharmaceutical, paper, mining, and construction industries.

In scientific research on maize breeding worldwide, considerable attention is paid to developing promising early-maturing varieties and hybrids with high grain and green-mass yields, resistance to diseases and pests, and improved seed-production systems.

Under conditions of global climate change, the development and practical introduction of maize varieties resistant to different stress factors, including drought, diseases, and pests, have substantial scientific and practical significance for ensuring food security.

In Uzbekistan, local productive varieties of maize have been developed by plant breeders to supply the population with food, industry with raw materials, and livestock and poultry production with nutritious feed. Nevertheless, a large proportion of the area occupied by maize is still sown with imported seed.

The Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Seed Production” of 16 February 2019 and “On Breeding Achievements” of 29 August 2002, Presidential Decree No. PF-5853 of 23 October 2019 “On the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030”, Resolution No. PQ-3683 of 27 April 2018 “On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the Seed Production System in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, Resolution No. PQ-106 of 28 January 2022 “On Additional Measures for the Further Development of Seed Production of Agricultural Crops”, and other regulatory documents adopted in this field define the creation of new local maize varieties, alongside other agricultural crops, as a priority direction.

Presidential Decree No. PF-158 of 11 September 2023 “On the Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy” sets tasks such as sharply increasing productivity and profitability in agriculture, raising the average income obtained from one hectare to USD 5,000, increasing agricultural exports to USD 10 billion annually, and attracting a total of USD 15 billion of investment into the agrarian sector.

Scientific investigations aimed at developing effective innovative technologies for maize breeding and seed production have been conducted at leading research centers, institutions, and universities worldwide. These include institutions and organizations in the United States, Australia and CIMMYT, China, Pakistan, Serbia, Ukraine, Moldova, Yugoslavia, Hungary, Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Russia, Kazakhstan, as well as well-known international maize seed companies in the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, France, Serbia, and Hungary. In Uzbekistan, research has been carried out at the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources and at the Maize Breeding and Seed Production Scientific Experimental Station. Comprehensive breeding work on early-maturing maize varieties and hybrids has also been conducted by the Ukrainian Research Institute of Maize Production and the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources.

The results of these studies have scientifically and practically demonstrated that the use of hybrids, synthetic varieties, and populations in maize breeding makes it possible to create productive varieties that are early-maturing and resistant to cold, drought, diseases, and pests.

However, an analysis of previous research indicates that the scientific basis for hybridizing geographically distant maize samples with local varieties, creating new early-maturing and productive hybrids and varieties with high grain and green-mass yields, and improving their primary seed production has not yet been sufficiently developed by national researchers.

Maize plays an important role in satisfying food demand. In world agriculture, it is among the major crops after wheat and rice. In the 1990s, maize was cultivated on 109 million hectares worldwide, producing 412 million tonnes of output. Over the subsequent decade, the maize area increased to 146 million hectares, and gross production reached 686 million tonnes in 2003-2005. Among agricultural crops, maize occupies the third position, with a share exceeding 30%.

By cultivated area, maize ranks after wheat and rice globally. In Asia, maize is cultivated on 55.0 million hectares; in North America, on more than 36.8 million hectares; in Africa, on 27.8 million hectares; in South America, on 25.5 million hectares; and in Europe, on 12.3 million hectares. In 2019, the United States ranked first in maize area with 35.5 million hectares, China second with 33.2 million hectares, and Brazil third with 15.3 million hectares. In Uzbekistan, the maize area in 2014 was 35.5 thousand hectares, with a yield of 50 c/ha.

Maize is considered a crop of American origin. The first written information about maize was recorded by Christopher Columbus during the discovery of America in 1492. At that time, dent, starchy, sweet, and popcorn groups of maize were known. Subsequently, maize began to spread throughout the world as a cultivated crop.

The history of maize origin covers a long period. Under favorable cultivation conditions, maize can produce high grain yields. In nature, maize has almost no independent mechanism for reproduction and adaptation to the external environment; under ordinary natural conditions, most plants perish and do not produce a harvest.

To date, science has not identified the wild ancestors of maize with certainty, and its origin spans millennia. This is supported by data from radioactive decay analysis of 5,000-year-old maize cobs found in Mexico. Some sources indicate that maize may have originated in the mountainous regions of Peru, Bolivia, and Ecuador, where many local forms of maize are found.

Other studies recognize southern Mexico and Central America as the center of origin of maize, because these regions contain teosintes with a chromosome number similar to maize ($2n = 20$) and numerous local forms related to them.

In Central Asia, maize began to be cultivated in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries. Early records of maize cultivation in the Fergana Valley were made by Votkhonu (1835) and Chekotillo (1931). As in Transcaucasia and Moldova, maize was not widely grown as a main crop across large areas in Central Asian countries. It was planted around field borders and among fruit, vegetable, and melon crops. The local population paid greater attention to sorghum than to maize, using its green mass as livestock feed and its grain for food.

The first variety-testing experiments on maize in Uzbekistan were conducted by M.M. Bushuev and R.R. Schroeder in 1910-1914 at the experimental plots of the desert zones and at Turkestan agricultural experimental stations. Until 1917, maize was not widely distributed in Uzbekistan because local flint and semi-dent forms were low-yielding. Maize was planted on small areas in the Fergana Valley and in Syrdarya. Later, N.N. Ballashev studied 43 maize varieties at the Uzbekistan Agricultural Station. In addition, S.K. Samokhvalenko at the Uzbekistan Research Institute of Animal Husbandry and F.S. Parkhomenko at the Uzbekistan Research Institute of Cotton Growing studied maize collection samples at the former SoyuzNIKHI Central Experimental Station.

Increasing maize productivity is an important global objective. To achieve this, breeders need to create high-yielding varieties and hybrids. Breeding is understood as the purposeful selection and creation by humans of plant varieties that can be used for food and animal feed.

Regarding the importance of breeding, N.I. Vavilov described plant breeding as “evolution created by human hands”.

In terms of feed and productivity quality, maize is one of the most valuable crops in the world. By land area, it ranks third after wheat and rice, occupying more than 114.5 million hectares and accounting for 31% of the global cultivated area.

America accounts for 45.7% of total maize grain production, more than two-thirds of which is produced in the United States, where the highest grain yields in the world, 5.3-7.5 t/ha, are obtained.

Maize grain is also one of the main crops in Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, Colombia, Venezuela, Paraguay, Peru, Guatemala, and Honduras; however, grain yields in these countries are relatively low, at 1.2-2.0 t/ha.

In Asia, maize occupies 38.6 million hectares, with an average yield of 2.8 t/ha, an annual gross output of 107.2 million tonnes, and a 26.4% share of world production. The main grain producer in Asia is China, accounting for 63.8%, with yields of 3.0-3.9 t/ha.

In the CIS countries, maize occupies 4.2 million hectares, with an average yield of 3.8 t/ha and a global share of 3.1-3.9%.

In Uzbekistan, 895.5 thousand tonnes of maize grain and 29.4 thousand tonnes of white sorghum grain were produced in 2024.

According to analyses by agricultural economists, the cultivation of agricultural crops, including maize, under the conditions of Uzbekistan is highly profitable. In addition to maize grain, its leaves and stems are valuable feed for livestock, and maize also plays an important role in satisfying the population's food demand.

2. Materials and Methods

Research on maize was conducted during 2010-2021 at the Maize Breeding and Seed Production Scientific Experimental Station in Zangiota district, Tashkent region. The climate of Tashkent region is sharply continental and is characterized by abundant heat and light throughout the growing season. According to observations of the Tashkent Observatory, average annual sunshine duration is 2,870 hours; the maximum duration occurs in summer and reaches up to 380 hours in July, or 95% of the possible value. Winter is relatively unstable, with cold periods alternating with warm periods.

The average duration of the period with air temperatures above 0°C is 330 days, while the vegetation period for heat-loving plants, defined by temperatures above 10°C, is 214 days.

Summers are hot and dry. In the hottest month, July, the average monthly air temperature is 28-29°C. The abundance of thermal resources, heat, and light in the artificially irrigated conditions of the Tashkent oasis makes it possible to obtain accurate data by applying intensive cultivation and processing technologies to different heat-loving plants, including maize.

During the experimental years, air temperature was favorable for maize growth and development. According to long-term averages, total precipitation was 35.1 mm, most of which occurred in late autumn, winter, and early spring. Stable snow cover is observed only in some winters; its thickness does not exceed 10-12 cm and it remains for 30-34 days. In most years, snow cover is uneven and melts quickly. The climate is dry, and the main share of precipitation falls in winter and spring. The highest precipitation is observed in March. The continental nature of the climate is reflected in annual, monthly, and daily meteorological variation across different years.

Total precipitation during the experimental years was lower than the long-term average. In 2018, precipitation was 35.9 mm, with the lowest value, 0.4 mm, recorded in July. The highest annual average precipitation was observed in 2016, at 39.9 mm.

In the maize experiments, no precipitation was observed during the flowering period, namely in August.

Table 1. Agrochemical characteristics of the experimental field soil at the Maize Breeding and Seed Production Scientific Experimental Station, Zangiota district, Tashkent region

Soil layer, cm	Humus, %	Nitrogen, %	Phosphorus, %	Potassium, %	CO ₂ , %	Mobile nitrogen, mg/kg	Mobile phosphorus, mg/kg	Mobile potassium, mg/kg
0-30	0.927	0.063	0.275	0.682	7.87	16.2	20.8	132.0
30-50	0.542	0.036	0.250	0.682	7.81	9.4	7.36	103.0

To conduct in-depth scientific research in this area, experiments were carried out in the experimental field of the Maize Breeding and Seed Production Scientific Experimental Station in Zangiota district, Tashkent region.

The experimental field consisted of typical sierozem soil with a heavy loam mechanical composition. The 30-cm arable layer was moderately supplied with total nutrient reserves: humus 1.2%, nitrogen 0.1%, phosphorus 0.160%, and potassium 1.60%. The amounts of mobile forms of phosphorus, potassium, and nitrates in the 0-30 cm soil layer were as follows: P₂O₅ - 35.5 mg/kg, K₂O - 290 mg/kg, and N₂O₃ - 28.2 mg/kg; in the 30-50 cm layer, the corresponding values were 32 mg/kg, 180 mg/kg, and 8.25 mg/kg (Table 1).

The moisture capacity of the soil in this field was 22%, and groundwater occurred at a depth of 13-15 m.

The experiments used the new promising high-grain-yielding maize variety “Kelajak 100”, included in the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In developing this variety, “VC 6661” was used as the maternal form and “MJ 600” as the paternal form.

The high-green-mass-yielding variety “Esdalik 80” was also used; in creating this variety, the maternal form was “Uzbekistan 100” and the paternal form was the “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid. Repeated crosses were conducted using the simple hybridization method.

The research methods were mainly laboratory and field based. The scientific studies used the generally accepted field-laboratory experiments and phenological observations described in the methodological manual “Methods of Field Experiments with Maize” (Dnipropetrovsk, 1984). Seed-quality indicators were determined according to O‘zDSt 2823:2014, “Seeds of Agricultural Crops: Methods for Determining Germination”.

In addition, the following methods were used: “Methodology of Breeding Experiments with Maize” by I.V. Savchenko (2012); the guidance on “Duration of the Vegetation Period and Valuable Economic Traits of New Early-Maturing Maize Hybrids” of the Uzbekistan Research Institute of Plant Science (2010); the method of individual selection in primary seed-production work of the All-Russian Research Institute of Grain Crops; and the phytopathological methods of Chumakov A.E. et al., “Basic Methods of Phytopathological Research” (Moscow, 1974), for identifying diseases.

The obtained results were statistically analyzed using B.A. Dospikhov’s “Methodology of Field Experiment” (Moscow, 1985) and modern ANOVA (analysis of variance). Yield was determined using StatView software (SAS Institute Inc.).

Agrotechnical measures in the experiment were developed on the basis of standard technological maps for the care of agricultural crops and production of agricultural output for 2016-2020.

As in other annual plants, the growth and development stages of maize are characterized by a series of successive morphological changes. The length of the growing season, the duration of each stage, and varietal traits of the plant are closely linked to the climatic conditions of the spring-summer-autumn period.

The more favorable the conditions for plant growth and development, the faster all life stages are completed; that is, the duration of each stage is shorter. Conversely, under unfavorable conditions, the plant remains longer in each developmental stage and its yield organs form more slowly.

To conduct the agrotechnical measures in the experimental field at the recommended times for cultivating maize varieties, the field was plowed to a depth of 28-30 cm.

Before plowing, 75% of the generally recommended phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were applied (P₂O₅ - 225 kg and KCl - 112.5 kg), while the remaining 25% (P₂O₅ - 75 kg and KCl - 37.5 kg) was applied together with seed sowing.

In early spring, the field was chiseled to a depth of 18-22 cm, leveled, and furrows and irrigation channels were prepared.

The prepared land plot was divided into experimental plots, and the seeds were sown manually. Because soil moisture was sufficient, pre-sowing irrigation was not applied.

The sown seeds germinated completely within 10-12 days. When the seedlings produced 4-5 leaves, the first cultivation was carried out at a depth of 10-12 cm.

During crop care, weeding was performed manually to control weeds, and light thinning was conducted to equalize plant density.

For the first fertilization, 230 kg of urea per hectare was applied and irrigation was carried out. When the plants produced 8-10 leaves, the second cultivation and fertilization were performed.

During the vegetation period, the maize crop was irrigated 5-6 times. Phenological observations were conducted from April to September, and the obtained results were recorded in the field journal.

3. Results and Discussion

As a result of high-quality implementation of all agrotechnical measures, mineral fertilization, inter-row cultivation, control of diseases and pests, and irrigation, the “Kelajak 100” variety produced 9.63 t/ha of grain, or up to 2.3 c/ha more grain yield than the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid.

According to agricultural economists, maize cultivation is a competitive crop under the conditions of Uzbekistan. In addition, because maize leaves and stems, apart from its grain, serve as a feed source for livestock, the crop provides additional economic benefit.

When the funds spent on cultivating agricultural crops under the conditions of Uzbekistan are compared with exchange prices, cotton, maize, and wheat occupy leading positions under irrigated conditions and are considered economically efficient crops.

The costs incurred, income received, and net profit obtained from producing commercial grain of the promising “Kelajak 100” maize variety on 1 ha under production conditions were calculated relative to the standard variety. The results are presented in Table 2.

In the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid, net profit was 17.7 million UZS/ha, whereas in the promising “Kelajak 100” variety it was 25.3 million UZS/ha. The profitability level was 108.2% and 154.6%, respectively.

According to the calculations, the new maize variety “Kelajak 100” was economically efficient for grain production and is recommended for cultivation to obtain high maize grain yield.

Table 2. Economic efficiency of grain production from maize varieties and hybrids

No.	Crop/indicator	Unit	Standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid	“Kelajak 100” variety	Difference, +/-
1	Sown area	ha	1	1	0
2	Total maize grain yield	t	8.4	10.7	+2.3
	Income from maize grain (3,500 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	29,400	37,450	+8,050

No.	Crop/indicator	Unit	Standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid	“Kelajak 100” variety	Difference, +/-
3	Dry fodder	t	23.4	21.2	-2.2
	Value (200 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	4,680.0	4,240.0	-440
4	Total income	thousand UZS	34,080.0	41,690.0	+7,610.0
5	Production costs				
5.1	Seed	kg	25	25	0
	Value (15,000 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	375.0	375.0	0
5.2	Mineral fertilizers, total				
5.2.1	Urea	kg	460	460	0
	Value (4,600 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	2,116.0	2,116.0	0
5.2.2	Phosphorus	kg	469	469	0
	Value (8,000 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	3,752.0	3,752.0	0
5.2.3	Potassium	kg	153	153	0
	Value (2,500 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	0.383	0.383	0
6	Organic fertilizer (manure)	t	20	20	0
	Value (300 UZS/t)	thousand UZS	6.0	6.0	0
7	Diesel fuel	L	169.5	169.5	0
	Value (9,500 UZS/L)	thousand UZS	1,610.2	1,610.2	0
8	Total cost	thousand UZS	14,235.7	14,235.7	0
9	Unexpected costs (15% of total cost)	thousand UZS	2,148.8	2,148.8	0
10	All costs	thousand UZS	16,371.1	16,371.1	0
11	Profit	thousand UZS	17,708.9	25,318.9	+7,610.8
12	Profitability level	%	108.2	154.6	+46.4 p.p.

Similarly, under production conditions, the costs incurred, income obtained, and net profit from cultivating the promising “Esdalik 80” variety for green mass (silage) on 1 ha were calculated relative to the standard variety. The results are presented in Table 3.

For green-mass production, net profit was 13.9 million UZS/ha in the standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety and 16.9 million UZS/ha in “Esdalik 80”. The profitability level was 89.9% for the standard variety and 108.9% for “Esdalik 80”.

The new promising maize variety “Esdalik 80” was evaluated as economically efficient for green-mass (silage) production and was recommended for cultivation across the republic.

Table 3. Economic efficiency of green-mass production from maize varieties and hybrids

No.	Crop/indicator	Unit	Standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety	“Esdalik 80” variety	Difference, +/-
1	Sown area	ha	1	1	0
2	Silage mass yield	t	73.9	81.3	+7.4
	Total income (400 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	29,560	32,520	+2,960
3	Costs				
3.1	Seed	kg	30	30	0
	Value (15,000 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	450.0	450.0	0
4	Mineral fertilizers, total				
4.1	Urea	kg	460	460	0
	Value (4,600 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	2,116.0	2,116.0	0
4.2	Phosphorus	kg	469	469	0
	Value (8,000 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	3,752.0	3,752.0	0
4.3	Potassium	kg	153	153	0
	Value (2,500 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	382.5	382.5	0
4.4	Organic fertilizer, manure	t	20	20	0
	Value (300 UZS/kg)	thousand UZS	6,000	6,000	0
5	Diesel fuel	L	152.5	152.5	0
	Value (9,500 UZS/L)	thousand UZS	1,448.7	1,448.7	0
6	Total cost	thousand UZS	14,149.2	14,149.2	0

No.	Crop/indicator	Unit	Standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety	“Esdalik 80” variety	Difference, +/-
7	Unexpected costs (10% of total cost)	thousand UZS	1,414.9	1,414.9	0
8	All costs	thousand UZS	15,564.2	15,564.2	0
9	Profit	thousand UZS	13,995.8	16,955.8	+2,960
10	Profitability level	%	89.9	108.9	+19 p.p.

According to experiments conducted in 2019-2021 on the “Kelajak 100” variety grown for grain, seed germination energy ranged from 96.7% to 97.3%, while in the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid it ranged from 96.0% to 96.8%. Seed germination in “Kelajak 100” was 97.9-98.1%, while in the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid it was 97.5-97.8%.

The germination energy of seeds of the promising “Kelajak 100” variety and the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid showed that the average germination energy of “Kelajak 100” was 97.1%, which was 0.6% higher than that of the standard hybrid. Seed germination was also 0.3% higher than in the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid. The results show that, when developing new promising varieties and hybrids, an in-depth analysis of laboratory results helps preserve positive indicators and supports the long-term stability of varieties without loss of varietal traits.

In the newly developed promising “Esdalik 80” variety grown for green mass (silage), seed germination energy was 94.0-95.0%, while in the standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety it was 94.5-96.0%. Seed germination in “Esdalik 80” was 95.3-96.7%, whereas in “Uzbekistan 100” it ranged from 95.0% to 96.0%.

The data obtained for germination energy in the promising “Esdalik 80” and the standard “Uzbekistan 100” varieties show that the average germination energy of “Esdalik 80” was 94.7%, which was 0.4% higher than the standard. Its seed germination was also 0.5% higher than that of “Uzbekistan 100”.

The yield indicators of the newly developed promising “Kelajak 100” and “Esdalik 80” varieties were also high, and these varieties produced high results in all experimental plots where they were sown and tested (Table 4).

Table 4. Yield indicators of the new promising maize varieties “Kelajak 100” and “Esdalik 80”

No.	Location	Variety	2019	2020	2021	Average yield (c/ha)
	Grain production (wax-ripeness stage)					

No.	Location	Variety	2019	2020	2021	Average yield (c/ha)
1	Maize Breeding and Seed Production Scientific Experimental Station, Tashkent region	Kelajak 100	97.0	109.5	107.4	104.6
2	“Oqsuv” farm, Qurgontepa district, Andijan region	Kelajak 100	78.1	98.9	104.4	93.8
3	“Energo Nasl Chorva” farm, Khavos district, Syrdarya region	Kelajak 100	78.1	93.6	100.4	90.7
	Average yield					96.3
	Green mass for silage (milk-ripeness stage)					
1	Maize Breeding and Seed Production Scientific Experimental Station, Tashkent region	Esdalik 80	802	816	824	814

No.	Location	Variety	2019	2020	2021	Average yield (c/ha)
2	“Oqsuv” farm, Qurgontepa district, Andijan region	Esdalik 80	733	746	798	759
3	“Energo Nasl Chorva” farm, Khavos district, Syrdarya region	Esdalik 80	730	751	795	758
	Average yield					777

Because the economic indicators presented above were effective for farmers, the “Esdalik 80” maize variety was planted during 2019-2021 for silage and green mass on 7.0 ha at the “Oqsuv” farm in Qurgontepa district, Andijan region, and on 18.0 ha at the “Energo Nasl Chorva” farm in Khavos district, Syrdarya region. The variety produced 81.0 t/ha of green mass, which was 5.1-5.6 t/ha higher than the standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety.

According to the research results, the proper selection of parental forms and the analysis of their valuable economic traits in the development of new promising varieties and hybrids help preserve positive results and ensure that varieties remain stable for many years without losing their varietal characteristics.

4. Conclusion

High efficiency was achieved as a result of scientific research on the development of new early-maturing and high-yielding maize varieties and hybrids and the improvement of their primary seed production. The main conclusions are as follows:

1. The germination energy and seed germination were 97.1% and 98.1% in “Kelajak 100”, 96.5% and 97.8% in the standard “Uzbekistan 601 ECB” hybrid, 94.7% and 95.9% in “Esdalik 80”, and 94.3% and 95.4% in the standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety. Compared with the standard, these indicators were 0.6% and 0.3% higher in “Kelajak 100” and 0.4% and 0.5% higher in “Esdalik 80”.

2. The “Kelajak 100” variety matured five days earlier than the standard variety; its grain yield was 2.3 c/ha higher, green-mass yield was 9 c/ha higher, and grain output was 2% higher, while its 1,000-grain weight was 22 g lower. The “Esdalik 80” variety matured six days earlier than the standard “Uzbekistan 100” variety; its grain and green-mass yields were 4.2 and 7.4 c/ha higher, and its grain output and 1,000-grain weight were 1% and 13 g higher, respectively.

3. Under production conditions, “Kelajak 100” produced 96.3 c/ha of grain, which was up to 2.3 c/ha more than the standard.

4. When the grain of the promising “Kelajak 100” variety was sold as commercial grain, net profit amounted to 25.3 million UZS/ha and profitability reached 154.6%. When the green

mass of the promising “Esdalik 80” variety was sold for silage, net profit per hectare was 16.9 million UZS/ha and profitability was 108.9%.

5. In addition, when “Kelajak 100” and the standard variety were grown for seed grain on 1 ha, net profit was 26.3 million UZS/ha in the standard variety and 36.3 million UZS/ha in “Kelajak 100”, with a profitability level of 217.4%.

6. When “Esdalik 80” was grown for seed production on 1 ha for silage purposes, net profit in “Esdalik 80” was reported as 36,488,000 UZS/ha and profitability was 209.6%.

7. The newly developed promising maize variety “Kelajak 100” is recommended for agricultural use for grain production, and “Esdalik 80” is recommended for green-mass production.

8. On the basis of results obtained in the primary seed-production system, it is proposed to improve the seed-production system and introduce a shortened four-year system in place of the existing five-year elite-seed production system.

REFERENCES

1. Massino, A. I., & Massino, I. A. (2015). Selection of hybrid maize for irrigated conditions of Uzbekistan [Selektsiya gibridnoy kukuruzy dlya oroshayemykh usloviy Uzbekistana]. Tashkent. 235 p. [in Russian].
2. Dwyer, L. M., & Stewart, D. W. (1984). Indicators of water stress in corn [*Zea mays* L.]. Canadian Journal of Plant Science, 64, 537-546.
3. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2019). Final data on maize harvest in the Republic in 2018. Tashkent, 21 February 2019. [in Uzbek/Russian].
4. Du Toit, L. J., & Pataky, J. K. (1999). Effects of silk maturity and pollination on infection of silks to maize ears by *U. maydis*. Plant Disease, 83(7), 621-626.
5. Chumak, M. V., & Suprunov, A. I. (2012). Combining ability of populations of different selection cycles for early flowering. Kukuруза i sorgo, 3, 9-12. [in Russian].
6. Vavilov, N. I. (1987). Theoretical foundations of breeding. Moscow: Nauka, 172-194. [in Russian].